

What Can Digital Preservation Learn from “Tequiology”?

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Abstract – This paper explores how the concept of ‘tequiology’, derived from Indigenous communal labour practices in Mexico, can inspire alternative approaches to digital preservation. Rooted in collective care, community organisation, and decolonial resistance, tequiology invites us to rethink preservation beyond Western-centric models. Through case studies of collaborative digital initiatives in Mexico, the paper demonstrates how community-driven methodologies can create inclusive, ecologically responsible, and socially embedded digital preservation practices

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I. INTRODUCTION

“Tequiology” [tequiología] is a concept adapted and adopted by Yásnaya Elena Aguilar Gil, a linguist and activist from Ayutla Mixe, Oaxaca, Mexico. It refers to how, from spaces of resistance, technology can be employed to strengthen the autonomies of Indigenous peoples and communities [1]. Through digital tools, “tequiology” seeks to *create common virtual spaces and to weave sustainable networks of collaboration among subaltern voices across the continent* [2]. The term derives from “tequio” (from the Nahuatl “tequitl”), a communal labour-practice in many regions of Mexico based on mutual support to meet everyday needs. In this sense, “tequiology” encompasses a wide range of what Aguilar calls *collaborative technologies in resistance* [3].

II. TEQUIOLOGY: RETHINKING DIGITAL PRESERVATION

There are multiple examples in Mexico where collaborative technologies are used to enable “digital activism” aimed at sustaining *re-existence* and resistance in communities [4]. The platform *Digital Activism for Indigenous Languages* supports Indigenous-language speakers in creating and promoting digital environments that are as diverse as their realities [5]. *Surciendo*, an organisation based in Chiapas, Mexico, promotes the use

of digitalities and open-source tools for community autonomy, digital rights, and feminist technologies (*hackfeminismos*) [6]. In Oaxaca, the initiative *Indigital* fosters political participation, digital rights, and access to information in Triqui, Mazateco, Mixe and Zapotec languages [7]. *The Virtual Museum of Zapoteco*, is a digital platform created to promote and disseminate knowledge related to Indigenous languages of Mexico, recognising them as intangible cultural heritage [8].

Beyond southern Mexico, the collective *Ronco Robles – Constructing Alternative Worlds* in the north supports projects such as *Community Mobile Phone Networks* and the *Observatory for Socio-environmental Conflicts in Chihuahua*, as a means of resistance and territorial defense [9].

III. REFRAMING THE PRACTICE OF DIGITAL PRESERVATION

But what would it mean to frame the practice of digital preservation through the lens of “tequiology”? At its core, it would require re-signifying digital preservation as a collaborative and daily acts of care, rooted in community logic to face and solve local needs. It would imply moving beyond a Western-centric, technocratic, and institutionalised narrative—one that is often framed by a patriarchal imaginary of the “heroic institution” that rescues THE memory of the world [10]. Instead, *tequiological preservation* proposes collective knowledge-making and knowledge-sharing processes to care digital commons. Envisioning tools that contribute to the creation of better technologies aimed at a more just and equitable society. Methodologies that enable situated and horizontal practices of digital preservation that care for territories, people, legacies, the environment, and diverse ways of living and understanding life.

IV. LOST IN TRANSLATION

In my experience, most digital preservation initiatives in Mexico led by memory institutions such as the National Archive (AGN), the National Library (BNM), and the National Newspaper Library (HNM) [11] tend to reproduce what Paola Ricaurte refers to as *sociotechnical assemblages of coloniality* [12]. These models are often grounded in logics of accumulation, the understanding of innovation as synonymous of progress, the assumption that technological solutions—primarily through the adoption of software—are sufficient, and a reliance on quantitative metrics as the sole indicators of success.

Their strategies mirror capitalist logics: they draw upon literature and conceptual frameworks developed in and for other contexts—specifically those of the Global North—which are then translated and imposed. In doing so, they reproduce patriarchal structures and reinforce hierarchies of knowledge. The problem is not simply translating from English to Spanish—or even into an Indigenous language—the dominant discourse of digital preservation. It is about critically questioning how *systems of oppression: patriarchy, colonialism, and capitalism* [13] shape what is preserved, how it is preserved, and who preserves it.

For example, Daria Mariscal, a woman from the Indigenous community *Paipai* in Baja California, Mexico, inherited from her grandmother and mother not only her native language, but also the cultural knowledge and practices that shape a particular way of understanding and inhabiting the world [14]. Through oral transmission and embodied experience, she learned the process related with the making of traditional *Paipai's* ceramics. Over time, however, the storytelling that once guided her hands in creating with clay have faded from memory. Today, Daria is one of the last speakers of *Paipai* and among the few who still understands the intricate fabric that sustains the *Paipai* imaginary—formed through the interwoven relationships between territory, ceramics, and language [15].

While the community *Paipai* face devastating changes brought about by capitalist consumption and the tangible effects of climate crisis on their territory, in 2017 the Mexican state proudly facilitated the deposit of part of the nation's legacy—encoded through digitization processes on 35mm film reels—into the *Arctic World Archive*. The *National Archive* (AGN) publicly celebrated this initiative, justifying it as a safeguard (for over 500 years) to ensure that, *in the event of a global catastrophe, this memory could still be retrieved, even if only a single copy remained or the original technological infrastructure for its playback no longer existed* [16].

Yet, the catastrophe is already unfolding. The knowledge embedded in territories—held and transmitted across generations—is disappearing in real time. While this happens, memory institutions continue to invest in digital preservation projects shaped by colonial epistemologies: frameworks that conceive memory as something to be frozen, abstracted, and secured within energy-intensive infrastructures.

Unfortunately, it is not only the legacies of Indigenous communities that are at risk. Today, our collective contemporary digital history faces one of its greatest threats. Numerous initiatives led by the U.S. government are not only actively erasing historical records [17] but also enabling the transformation of everyday digital spaces—such as social media—into what Simona Levi calls *private extractive latifundia* [18]. These spaces function primarily as repositories of data for extraction, thus enabling a new mode of domination: the colonialism of data [19].

V. A CALL FOR DECOLONIAL APPROACHES

Can we imagine digital preservation beyond colonial logic? If framed through “tequiology”, digital preservation would seek to empower communities with knowledge and tools to sustain autonomy. Orality, sonority and storytelling—central to Indigenous epistemologies—would gain a legitimate place within preservation practices. Preservation becomes daily acts of care, grounded in locally adapted and collectively driven methodologies that incorporate open-source technologies, grassroots documentation, and environmental sustainability. Digital preservation would advocate for digital sovereignty, recognizing and incentivizing decentralized, shared, public digital infrastructures and tools.

VI. COLLECTIVE MODELS IN PRACTICE

Such “tequiological approaches” are already evident in projects like *Huellas Incómodas*, a collaborative web archiving initiative that documents and contextualises feminist social struggles across Latin America [20]. The collective began within an academic context, with a local scope and by using accessible web-archiving tools to document feminist activism within the student movement in Toluca, Mexico. This model of organisation—rooted in identifying a need, gathering together, collectivising knowledge, and building community—has enabled *Huellas Incómodas* to evolve into a self-managed platform where feminist collectives preserve their own digital information.

Defensores de la Democracia (DDL) is another powerful example: the first and only digital repository to gather, preserve and catalogue the work of journalists

murdered in Mexico between 2000 and 2023 [21]. Like *Huellas Incómodas*, the project began within an academic context, making use of accessible web archiving tools to document the work of journalists on social media platforms. Once again, self-management and community-based organisation—grounded in collective care and resistance—have ensured the sustainability and ongoing relevance of the platform.

Another important initiative is the digital archive *Catálogo de Indicios*. [22]. The archive documents clothing, personal hygiene items, suitcases, and other belongings found at Rancho Izaguirre. The collective *Guerreros Buscadores de Jalisco*, a grassroots group dedicated to the search for missing persons in Mexico, conducted a review of the site and concluded that it had been used by drug trafficking networks to torture and cremate victims. The State later closed off access to the property, preventing families from identifying whether the recovered objects might belong to their missing relatives. The digital platform allows families to identify items belonging to missing persons. This initiative stands as a powerful example of how collective organisation, collaborative efforts, and the defense of the common good can confront the violence inflicted by the State—violence that is often silenced or denied by official institutions.

VII. CONCLUSION

Tequiology urges us to understand digital preservation not as a technological fix or institutional protocol, but as a living, socially embedded, and ecologically responsible practice. It invites us to build communities and daily acts of care rather than systems of control and hierarchical structures as means to preserve not only data, but memory, dignity, and life itself.

In the spirit of *tequiological preservation* together with five students from the Visual Arts programme at ENPEG La Esmeralda, we created the zine *Cuidados Digitales* [23] This zine seeks to acknowledge digital preservation as practices and knowledges rooted in networks of mutual care and support, collectively organised to safeguard the digitalities that matter to the community we inhabit. We reflected on our experiences engaging with digital tools that can be used in service of the common good, collective memory, and affective forms of sociality, such as Fediverse platforms, PDA guides, and the WebRecorder suite. Through this process, we began to reimagine digital preservation as an act of care—rooted in daily life, sustained by community, and driven by a commitment to memory, dignity, and the defense of the digital commons.

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